

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid by dichromate in presence and absence of succinic acid

A. S. Kulkarni^{a*}, B. K. Bongane^a, P. G. Gavali^a and (Mrs.) N. T. Patel^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry and Physics, B. S. College, Basmath-431 512, Dist. Hingoli, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : as_kulkarni123@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Yeshwant College, Nanded-431 602, Maharashtra, India

Manuscript received 27 January 2011, accepted 09 January 2012

Abstract : The effect of varying concentration of [substrate], [oxidant], $[H^+]$, added neutral salt have been studied. It has been found that, the order of reaction with respect to [oxidant] and [substrate] found to be unity from the slope of plots $\log k$ vs $\log [\text{sub}]$. The rate of reaction increases with decrease in pH of perchloric acid. Hammett's acidity function and activity of water have been studied. Effect of temperature has been studied. Activation parameters were computed. The plot of ΔH^* vs ΔS^* is linear. The effect of dielectric constant of the medium indicates the reaction to be +ve ion-dipole. The result of oxidation products have been identified.

Keywords : Kinetics, succinic acid, syringic acid, 4-methoxycinnamic acid, Hammett acidity function.

Experimental

The oxidation of a number of α -hydroxy acids has been studied with $[Cr^{VI}]$ ^{1,2}. A detailed study on the oxidation of organic acids containing substituted groups at *para* positions has not been attempted. As a part of our research programme, this paper incorporates our kinetic results on $[Cr^{VI}]$ oxidation of syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid.

Materials and methods :

Organic materials, substituted acids were s.d. fine (A.R.) grade glacial acetic acid (A.R.) was used as the solvent. All inorganic materials including chromic acid, $HClO_4$ (60%) were A.R. grade. Doubly distilled water was used for preparing different compositions of solvent. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Kinetic measurements :

The rate of consumption of $[Cr^{VI}]$ was followed colorimetrically by measuring the optical density at 420 nm on a MAC digital photoelectric colorimeter. Requisite volumes of reactants previously equilibrated at 30 °C within ± 0.01 °C were mixed and immediately transferred to the cell. The optical densities were recorded at different time of intervals. The ionic strength of the medium was adjusted by adding requisite quantity of sodium chloride. The kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo-first

order conditions and the first order rate constant was calculated from the slope of the linear plot of $\log [Cr^{VI}]$ vs time and values reproducible to 2–3%.

Results and discussion

Effect of varying $[H^+]$: In order to study the effect of $[H^+]$, the experiments were carried out at different $[HClO_4]$ while keeping the [substrate], $[Cr^{VI}]$ constant. The results show a proportional dependence on $[H^+]$ ions. It is observed that $[H^+]$ ions are responsible for the increase in rate³ (Table 1). The plots of $\log k$ vs $\log [H^+]$ (Fig. 1) are found to be linear in the case of syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid where the slopes are significantly nearly one.

Hammett's acidity function represents the ability of a solvent to donate a proton to neutral base. In dilute solution $H_0 = -\log a_{H^+} = pH$, therefore for pure water $H_0 = pH = 7$ at 25 °C. As the acidity of the solution increases, the value of H_0 decreases in order to get a mechanistic interpretations of acid catalysed reactions, the Hammett's acidity function (H_0) is used.

A linear plot between $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $-H_0$ for both uni-molecular and bimolecular reaction indicate the increase in concentration of $[HClO_4]$, exhibit a uniform increase in pseudo-first order rate constant indicate that the reactions are acid-catalysed gives unit slopes. This

Table 1. Effect of varying $[H^+]$ on reaction rate
 $[Cr^{VI}] = 5 \times 10^4 M$, $\mu = 0.3030 M$, $[HOAc] = 20\%$, Temp. = $30^\circ C$

$[H^+]$ (M)	$\log a_w$	H_0	Syringic acid		4-Methoxycinnamic acid	
			$k \times 10^3$	$H_0 + \log k$	$k \times 10^3$	$H_0 + \log k$
0.730	-0.0120	+0.30	16.79	-1.475	6.579	-1.818
0.909	-0.0165	+0.05	19.57	-1.658	8.690	-2.011
1.090	-0.0200	-0.12	21.71	-1.780	10.468	-2.100
1.273	-0.0240	-0.25	23.03	-1.890	11.515	-2.185
1.455	-0.0280	-0.40	28.34	-1.948	14.393	-2.242
1.818	-0.0380	-0.60	41.74	-1.980	18.424	-2.335

hypothesis known as Zucker-Hammett hypothesis⁵. Plot of $[\log k + H_0]$ vs $\log a_w$ gives a straight line, positive value of parameter ω (Fig. 1) greater than +3.3, indicates that water behaves as proton transfer agent in the rate controlling step⁶.

Fig. 1. (A,B) Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [H^+]$ and (C,D) plot of $-[\log k + H_0]$ vs $-\log a_w$: (●) syringic acid ($\omega = 35$), (Δ) 4-methoxycinnamic acid ($\omega = 11.76$), A = slope = 1.2, B = slope = 1.3.

Effect of varying [oxidant] : The reaction was studied at varying oxidant concentrations and the order with respect to oxidant was found to be one. The first order rate constant showed that rate constant decreases with increasing the initial $[Cr^{VI}]$ (Table 2). This suggests that $HCrO_4^-$ is oxidising reacting species of Cr^{VI} 7,8.

Table 2. Effect of varying $[Cr^{VI}]$ on reaction rate

$[Cr^{VI}] \times 10^4$ (M)	Syringic acid $k \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	4-Methoxycinnamic acid $k \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)
2.87	10.52	5.234
2.72	12.56	6.579
2.57	15.35	7.676
2.42	17.27	9.212
2.27	22.75	10.966
2.12	27.53	12.120
1.96	33.26	15.353
1.81	38.38	20.936

$$\text{Rate law : } \frac{-d [Cr^{VI}]}{-dt} = k [Cr^{VI}] [\text{substrate}]$$

The decreasing trend in the rate constant may be due to the hydrolytic equilibrium between $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ and $HCrO_4^-$, the molecular identity of $[Cr^{VI}]$ species present in the solution as given below :

In addition to the above species there may be other species, since the reaction has been carried out in acetic acid-water medium, $[Cr^{VI}]$ is also expected to exist in the form of an acetyl chromate $AcOCrO_3^-$.

Effect of varying [substrate] : The rate of oxidation increased with increasing concentration of the substrate. The plots of $1/k$ vs $1/[sub]$ are linear and do not pass through the origin but show definite intercepts at $1/k_{obs}$ axis (Fig. 2 and slope = 1, of line A and B). This indicates evidence for complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate⁹.

Fig. 2. (A,B) Plot of $3 + \log k$ vs $3 + \log [\text{sub}]$ and (C,D) plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{acid sub.}]$: (●) syringic acid, (Δ) 4-methoxycinnamic acid, A = slope = 1.0, B = slope = 0.75.

Fig. 3. (A,B) Plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T \times 10^3$ K and (C,D) plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$: (●) syringic acid, (Δ) 4-methoxycinnamic acid, (●) = $E_a = 4.816 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, (Δ) = $E_a = 10.296 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

Effect of varying [ionic strength] : On increasing ionic strength by adding sodium chloride the rate decreases. The plot of $[\log k - \log k_0]$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$, indicates that the reaction is between oppositely charged reactants¹⁰. The acid chromate-dichromate equilibrium constant is a function of the ionic strength, increase in ionic strength will favour the formation of weak oxidising chlorochromate species than HClO_4^- dichromate ion and this will decrease the rate of reaction.

Effect of varying [solvent] : It is observed that the rate of oxidation increases with the increasing percentage of acetic acid in water. The reaction has been carried out in acetic acid medium, $[\text{Cr}^{VI}]$ dissolved in high percentage of acetic acid may also exist in the form of an acetyl chromate ion ($\text{AcO}^-\text{CrO}_3^-$). Solvent dependence on rate indicates a superior oxidising species. The plots of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ (Fig. 3) are linearly related as expected for +ve ion-dipole reaction¹¹, the attacking species is considered to be HCrO_3^+ .

Effect of varying temperature : The pseudo-first order rate constants of oxidation of syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid were determined at different temperatures. The plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 3) are linear and the heat of activation were calculated from these plots. The reactions are as a whole characterized by a wide range of parameters. The activation parameters E_a , ΔH^* ,

Table 3. Activation parameters

Parameters	Syringic acid	4-Methoxycinnamic acid
E_a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	4.816	10.296
ΔH^* (kcal mol ⁻¹)	4.214	9.694
ΔS^* (e.u.)	-60.342	-43.59
ΔG (kcal mol ⁻¹)	22.497	22.901
A (s ⁻¹)	0.1099×10^4	5.105×10^3

ΔS^* , ΔG^* , were evaluated (Table 3).

In the presence of succinic acid (dibasic acid) :

Effect of varying dibasic acid : The kinetic of oxidation of organic acid in presence of succinic acid ionize into two steps and increase the acidity of the reaction, in order to enhance the reaction,

Hence the increase in concentration of succinic acid, increases the rate of reaction because of the electron-withdrawing effect of second -COOH group enhances the acidity of the first COOH¹².

Conclusions :

The positive values of enthalpy of activation ($k\Delta H^*$) indicates the reaction are endothermic in nature. The activation energy is highest for the slowest reaction suggesting that the oxidation reactions are enthalpy controlled¹³. The negative entropy of activation ($k\Delta S^*$) indicates the oxidation of these reactions are entropy controlled¹³. The plot of ΔH^* vs ΔS^* is linear.

In the oxidation of syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid by chromic acid, the frequency factor lies in the ranges of 0.199×10^1 to 5.105×10^3 . Hence, reactions can be described as normal reactions and to suggest that the reactions are not of bimolecular type¹⁴.

The reaction products aldehydes were identified. The kinetic of oxidation of syringic acid is found to have higher than 4-methoxycinnamic acid. The activation energy is the highest for the slowest reaction suggesting that, the oxidation reactions are enthalpy controlled. The *p*-oriented substituents -OH, -OCH₃, show faster reaction kinetics of syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid.

Mechanism : The formation of free radical was neither indicated in the initial stage of the reaction nor at the later stage by addition of mercuric chloride in the rate-determining step. It is therefore reasonable to assume that the reaction of acid syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid proceeds through simple two electron transfer oxidant.

In consideration of the above discussions stoichiometry and products formed, the reaction mechanism syringic acid and 4-methoxycinnamic acid with HCrO_4^- can be explained by much simpler mechanism shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

(in presence of succinic acid)

Scheme 2

References

1. G. V. Bakore and S. N. Narain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3419.
2. K. K. Sen Gupta, A. K. Chatterjee and S. P. Moulik, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1970, **43**, 3841.
3. Kalyan K. Sen Gupta, Ashis K. Chatterjee, (Mrs.) Tapati Sarkar and (Mrs.) Shipra Sen Gupta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 1024.
4. L. Zucker and L. P. Hammett, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2729.
5. Raj K. Bansal, "Organic Reaction Mechanism", Tata McGraw Hill Pub. Co. Ltd., New Delhi, 1978, pp. 92-93.
6. K. R. Jennings and R. B. Cundall, "Progress in Reaction Kinetics", Vol. 6, 1972, pp. 155.
7. K. B. Willberg and T. J. Mill, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3022.
8. K. K. Sen Gupta, J. R. Chatterjee and A. K. Chatterjee, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 901.
9. N. K. Saran, M. M. Dash and R. C. Acharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **18**, 225.
10. E. S. Amis, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1966, 24.
11. S. Sundaram and N. Venkatasubramanian, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1102.
12. "A Text Book of Organic Chemistry" by Arun Bahl, p. no. 379 (Acidity).
13. Ranveer Singh and S. K. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1998, **10**, 749.
14. Vijay P. Singh, Indra M. Pandey and Subhash B. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 64.